

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF GRAPHENE COATED GLASS FIBERS AND CARBON NANOTUBE FORESTS AS EMBEDDED STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a graphene-coating on glass fiber weave has been evaluated as a multifunctional sensing material based on previous work performed by the authors on embedded vertically aligned carbon nanotube forests. First, the graphene-coating has been assessed as a resistive cure-monitoring sensor when embedded in thermosetting glass fiber/epoxy laminate to monitor its production. The graphene-coating showed similar results to the resistive cure monitoring of carbon nanotubes. However, the graphene-coating diverges in its resistive signature upon reaching cure temperature, showing a continuous resistance decrease in this phase, suggesting a sensitivity to cure-induced shrinkage of the epoxy, not seen in the carbon nanotube sensor. Later, in the cured state, the embedded graphene-coating functions as an excellent temperature sensor, possessing a negative thermoresistive effect. However, as a strain sensor, the graphene-coating does not perform as well as the embedded carbon nanotube sensor, possessing an initial drift in resistance upon its first load cycle and additional drift during constant strain conditions, and when unloaded.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composites (FRPCs) have seen increased use within the aerospace, automotive and wind turbine sectors due to their high specific modulus and strength. Together with their increased implementation, the interest in monitoring FRPC structures has increased. This includes monitoring the production of the components, performing cure monitoring, and later structural health monitoring (SHM) during their operational lifetime. To perform SHM, the possibility of monitoring strain, temperature, pressure, and more, experienced by the component is of interest.

FRPCs have the possibility to embed sensors in their structure, obtaining multifunctionality. However, when embedding a sensor into the composite structure, the sensor's size is critical to not interfere with, or deteriorate, the mechanical structure. Preferably, the embedded sensor should be mechanically non-intrusive and possess the ability to perform in-situ online cure monitoring during production of the component for quality and process control. Thereafter, in the cured state, the sensor should be used for other types of sensing, i.e. for structural health monitoring (SHM).

In parallel, new sensitive resistive sensors have been envisioned using carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphene-based sensors. Research using CNT-based sensors for strain [1–4] and temperature [3,5] sensing, and cure monitoring [4,6,7] has been published. Similarly, graphene-based sensors have been

studied for strain [8–13] and temperature [8,13–15] sensing and cure monitoring [6,13,16]. In these papers, using CNTs and/or graphene, the sensors have been achieved through modification of the matrix with fillers [1,5,8], fiber-coatings [4,6,13,16], vertically aligned CNT (VACNT) forests [3,7], CNT buckypapers [2], and graphene films [10–12,14,15]. Although much work has been done on graphene-based sensors, limited work exists where graphene-based sensors have been embedded into FRPCs for sensing [6,9,13,16].

In this paper, a graphene-based sensor is embedded into glass fiber/epoxy laminate and evaluated as a resistive sensor. The sensor is compared to previous work conducted by our group studying VACNT forests as embedded resistive sensors. This paper presents initial results on the sensing capabilities of the graphene-based as a 1) cure-monitoring, 2) temperature and 3) strain sensor.

2. Method

2.1 Material

In this work, the glass fiber/epoxy prepreg used was HexPly6376-G-120 from Hexcel. The HexPly6376-G-120 has a fiber volume fraction of 42 %, the weave being a 4-harness satin weave, HexForce 120. In addition, the HexPly 6376 (36g/m²) epoxy adhesive film was used.

Two materials were used for resistive sensing. First, VACNT forests were used, grown on stainless steel substrate provided by N12 Technologies and used as received. The VACNT forest has been studied in previous work, determining the individual CNTs to contain 7 ± 2 walls and an outer diameter of 8 ± 2 nm. In the same work, the volume fraction of CNTs in the VACNT forest was determined to be 0.4 %; please see [3] for more details. Secondly, a graphene-coated glass fiber weave, delivered by Grafren AB, was used. See section 2.3 for more details on the graphene-coated glass fiber weave.

A copper-nickel-coated non-woven carbon fiber veil from Technical Fibre Products Ltd (Carbon 20444A, 8g/m²) was used to establish contact with the resistive sensors.

2.2 Deposition of VACNT Forests

To embed the VACNT forest into laminates they were deposited on a prepreg surface. A vacuum bag and a heating plate were used to perform the deposition of the VACNT forest. The substrates with the VACNT forest were placed on the prepreg surface with the VACNT forest facing the prepreg surface. The prepreg was placed inside a vacuum bag, on top of a heating plate, and heated to 55°C. Upon reaching 55°C, vacuum was applied, pressing the substrate and VACNT forest into the prepreg's surface. Vacuum was held for a few seconds. Thereafter, the vacuum bag was opened and the substrates removed, leaving behind the VACNT forest deposited on the prepreg surface.

2.3 Graphene-Coated Glass Fiber Weave

Electrically conductive inks with functionalized graphene (fG) were prepared according to Grafren's patented method [17]. Graphene fG ink was a graphene containing water dispersion with high electrical conductivity (up to 10 Ω /m² for 1 μ m thick coating). As the dispersion was water-based and free of adhesives, it could be applied to most surfaces. E-glass mats (Hexcel 7781 glass fiber weave) were tested and verified for application with this type of fG ink. The prepared ink was applied to the surface of the glass fiber using Grafren's method [18]. Each individual fiber was covered with nano-flakes of conductive graphene. After several successive surface treatment steps, a complete electrically conductive skin of flexible fG sheets was created. The flake had a nano-sized thickness and a surface spread of 1–3 μ m. These overlapped with each other and developed strong bonds between the functional groups in the adjacent flakes. The surface layer thickness achieved allowed high heat and electrical conductivity in the plane and out of the plane. This surface layer will from now on be referred to as the graphene-coating.

2.4 Sample Preparation

Samples with VACNT forests and graphene-coated glass fiber were prepared. The dimensions of all samples were 30x200 in-plane. The VACNT forest samples were 20 plies in thickness, with the VACNT forest being deposited on both prepreg surfaces facing each other in the midplane. During the lay-up, contacts of Carbon 20444A veil were placed in each, exiting the sample, to permit connectivity. In a similar way, the graphene-coated glass fiber weave was placed in the midplane, with 10 plies of HexPly6376-G-120 prepreps on each side. An extra layer of HexPly6376 epoxy adhesive film was added to one of the 10-ply stacks to aid with the wetting of the graphene-coated glass fiber weave. Contacts of Carbon 20444A veil were added and then subsequently cured, see 2.5. Three samples of each type were manufactured and studied in this work.

2.5 Cure Monitoring

The curing of the samples was performed using a vacuum-bag-only method inside an oven. The used cure cycle consisted of the following steps: 30 min at 30°C, followed by a temperature increase to 180°C, using a 2°C/min heat-up. Thereafter, the temperature was kept at 180°C for 2 hours and thereafter cooling down in the oven to room temperature. Full vacuum was applied during the whole curing cycle. A SP-50 Biologic Potentiostat, applying 10 V voltage, recording the current at 1 Hz, was used to monitor the resistive behavior of the embedded VACNT forests. Metallic interconnects were used to bridge the tacky tape and vacuum bag to connect the sample to the potentiostat. Two K-type thermocouples together with a NI9212 module from National Instruments via LabVIEW were used to register the temperature during the curing. The first thermocouple was placed in the oven, monitoring its temperature, the second was embedded in the mid-plane of a separate laminate of equal material and thickness as the samples, to measure the temperature at the placement of the resistive sensors.

2.6 Temperature Sensing

After curing, the samples were exposed to a temperature cycle to study their thermoresistive response. The test was performed using a ACS FM340C climate chamber. The climate chamber was programmed to decrease from 30°C to -70°C at 2°C/min and maintain -70°C during 15 min. Thereafter, the temperature increased 2°C/min to 150°C and was then maintained for 15 min. Lastly, the temperature decreased 2°C/min to 0°C. The resistance and temperature data were recorded as described in section 2.5.

2.7 Strain Sensing

The manufactured samples' piezoresistive response was evaluated performing quasi-static tensile testing together with continuous measurement of the sample's resistance. An Instron 4505 electromechanical tensile test machine was used for tensile testing together with a surface-mounted extensometer to measure the sample-strain. The samples were loaded 100 N/s, up until 0.5 % strain was reached, staying in the elastic region of the sample. The 0.5 % strain was maintained for 30 seconds, then unloaded with the same speed. This cycle was repeated for each sample 5 times. To perform resistive measurements, the SP-50 Biologic Potentiostat was used to record the current at a constant 10 V voltage using a sampling rate of 10 Hz.

3. Results and Discussion

In this work, the focus is evaluating the performance of the graphene-coating as a multifunctional sensor. This evaluation is based on previous work performed by the authors on VACNT forests for the same applications, namely, cure monitoring [7], and strain and temperature sensor [3].

3.1 Curing

To evaluate the cure monitoring capability of the graphene-coating, a previously established procedure for assessing the VACNT forest's capability has been used. The cure cycle has been divided into phases, based on the cure cycle's temperature. First, phase I is the initial 30 minutes under vacuum at 30°C. Phase II is the heat-up to curing temperature, which has been divided into two parts in [7] due to the significant resistive shift. The third phase corresponds to the time spent at the curing temperature.

Figure 1: Resistive cure monitoring of a) embedded CNTs b) graphene-coated glass fibers.

The decreasing resistance in phase I in Fig. 1a is caused by the consolidation of the laminate, the two VACNT forests in the midplane getting into better contact with each other, in addition to the slight increase of temperature to 30°C, both contributing to a lower resistance. In Fig. 1b, a small resistance decrease is also observed. Here, no significant impact of the consolidation is expected on the graphene coated on the glass fiber weave. Rather the slight resistance decrease is believed to be caused by the slight temperature increase, graphene having a negative thermoresistive effect [13]. In phase II A, Fig 1a, as the heat-up commences, there is first a slight decrease in resistance. This is, again, caused by the

temperature increase, before the viscosity of the prepreg's epoxy is lowered enough to fill the interspace between the embedded CNTs, causing the dramatic resistance increase seen later in phase IIA in Fig. 1a. In Fig. 1b, there is also an initial resistance decrease, which is also reasonably caused by the temperature increase. However, the resistance decrease is lasting into higher temperatures using the graphene-coating than the embedded CNTs. At around 62 min, the resistance turns around and increase slightly until reaching 90°C. We believe this is also caused by the partial infiltration of the epoxy into the graphene-coating. However, the graphene structure's epoxy infiltration is not expected to be as significant as for CNTs, only achieving partial infiltration as presented in [6], explaining the relatively low resistance increase observed in Fig. 1b compared to in Fig. 1a. Later, in phase II B, the resistance decrease in Fig. 1a was determined to be caused by the thermoresistive effect, decreasing as the temperature increased. The cure-induced shrinkage measured in [7] was concluded not to affect the resistive behavior directly. This is due to the resistive behavior observed in phase III, where the resistance increases, rather than decreases. A resistance decrease would have been expected if the embedded CNTs were significantly affected by the cure-induced shrinkage, resulting in a shorter inter-CNT distance. However, in Fig. 1b, the resistance decreases continuously. Initially, this is reasonably caused also by the thermoresistive effect, until approaching the cure temperature and phase III. Observing the resistance evolution over phase III for the graphene-coating, we observe a continuous resistance decrease over the whole phase, even though the temperature is stable. This may indicate a sensitivity to cure-induced shrinkage, which becomes more pronounced from 160° C, up until ca 15 minutes into the curing temperature, after that, it continues over its whole duration, but at a slower rate. Even though the epoxy infiltration is expected to be less significant in the graphene-coating than the embedded CNTs, the shrinkage of this epoxy is believed to still affect the resistive behavior. Similar observations have been made in [6].

3.2 Temperature Sensing

The thermoresistive response of representative samples of a) embedded CNTs and b) graphene-coated glass fiber weave is presented in Fig. 2 below.

Figure 2: Thermoresistive response between -70°C and 150°C for a) embedded CNTs and b) graphene-coating.

In both figures, it is obvious that the studied sensors have a significant resistive sensitivity to changes in temperature. The resistive signatures of the two sensors are close to identical, both having a negative thermoresistive effect, i.e. resistance decreasing as a response to a temperature increase.

3.3 Strain Sensing

The piezoresistive response of the two studied sensors is presented in Fig. 3. Fig. 3a presents the resistive changes observed for an embedded VACNT sensor, and Fig. 3b the resistive changes for the graphene-coated glass fiber weave.

Figure 3: Resistive strain sensing of a) embedded CNTs and b) graphene coating.

First studying Fig. 3a, a linear piezoresistive response to the strain is observed. The resistance is stable during the holds at 0.5 % strain, and when off-loaded, no resistance drifting is observed. This pattern is repeated over the five repetitions. Our previous work [3], showed that the piezoresistive effect of individual CNTs collectively produce the observed piezoresistive response seen here. Looking at the piezoresistive response of the graphene-coated glass fiber weave, Fig. 3b, a large resistance shift is observed in the first load-cycle, the sample's resistance not returning to its original value once off-loaded. However, the following load-cycles are repetitive, indicating the initial behavior to be a one-time occurrence, at least for this specific load-cycle. No explanation for this resistive behavior of the graphene-coating samples is presented in this work, requiring further studies. During the 0.5 % strain holds, the graphene-coating shows a resistance drift, the resistance increasing over time. This is similarly observed when off-loaded, the resistance decreasing slightly. Again, to determine why this resistive behavior is present more work is required. However, the authors suspect the nature of the epoxy infiltration into the graphene-coating on the glass fiber weave to be a cause of this, and plan to investigate this further in future work, and also the adherence of the graphene-coating to the individual glass fibers.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, the suitability of a graphene-coating on glass fiber weave as a multifunctional sensor is evaluated and compared to previous work performed by the authors on embedded VACNT forests. The graphene-coating has been evaluated as a cure-monitoring sensor when embedded in thermosetting glass fiber/epoxy laminate to monitor its production. The graphene-coating showed similar results to the cure monitoring of CNTs, the resistance being sensitive to its surrounding temperature and also believed to respond to partial epoxy infiltration of its structure. However, the graphene-coating diverges from the CNT sensor when kept at cure temperature, showing a continuous resistance decrease in this phase. This

possibly indicates a sensitivity to cure-induced shrinkage of the epoxy, which infiltrated the graphene structure earlier in the cure cycle. Later, in the cured state, the embedded graphene-coating functions as an excellent temperature sensor, possessing a negative thermoresistive effect. However, as a strain sensor, the graphene-coating does not perform as well as the compared-to embedded CNT sensor, possessing an initial drift in resistance upon its first load cycle and additional drift during constant strain conditions at 0.5 % strain, and when unloaded.

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